

E6.1 Validation Methodology and Infrastructure Setup

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Trust, Privacy & Security for 6G

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**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
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Dissemination Level

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Table of Contents

List of Acronyms	7
Executive Summary	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1 Target Audience	9
1.2 Document Structure	9
2. Validation Methodology	11
2.1 Validation Objectives	11
2.1.1 Security & Privacy Orchestration (i2CAT)	12
Scenario 1: Deploying Application with Integrated Security Policies	14
Scenario 2: Zero-Knowledge Proof-Based Authentication	14
2.1.2 Trust Model (UoC)	17
Scenario 1: Testing the Applicability of Trust Mechanisms Across Various Domains	18
Scenario 2: Testing the Efficiency of Evidence Registration and Reputation Computation	18
Scenario 3: Testing the Scalability of the Trust System	19
Scenario 4: Evaluating the Decentralization Capabilities of the Trust System	19
2.1.3 Privacy Framework (UoC)	22
Scenario 1: Assess the Delay Introduced by Privacy Mechanisms	23
Scenario 2: Assess the Time Taken to Configure Privacy Mechanisms	24
Scenario 3: Assess Added Delay and Transfer Rate with Noise Injection	24
Scenario 4: Evaluate the Trade-offs of Privacy Mechanisms	25
Scenario 5: Assess Privacy Mechanism Coverage	25
Scenario 6: Execute Privacy Attacks to Create Datasets for Training Models	25
2.1.4 Physical Layer Key Generation (Grad)	27
Scenario 1: Eavesdropping prevention in Wireless Communication environment	28
2.1.5 Detection, Classification, and Mitigation xApps (Grad)	31
Scenario 1: Anomaly Detection in an Open RAN Communications Environment	32
Scenario 2: Jamming Characterization in an Open RAN Communications Environment	32
Scenario 3: Anomaly Mitigation in an Open RAN Communications Environment	33
2.1.6 Security Controls for Programmable Forwarding Planes	34
Scenario 1: Packet Tampering	35
Scenario 2: Rule Injection	35
Scenario 3: Denial of Service (DoS)	36
Scenario 4: Adaptive Testing	36
2.2 Evaluation Planning	38

3. Infrastructure Testbed Setup	39
3.1 Introduction	39
3.1.1 Overview of Testbed Infrastructure	39
3.1.2 Objectives and Design Criteria	39
3.2 Testbed Infrastructure Components	40
3.2.1 Computing Nodes	41
3.2.2 Network Interconnection	41
3.2.3 Technological Foundation	42
3.3 Infrastructure Setup Process	43
3.3.1 Initial Configuration	43
3.4 Application Deployment	46
3.4.1 Deployment Strategies	46
4. Conclusion	48
5. References	49

List of Figures

Figure 1: Gantt chart	38
Figure 2: Testbed Components	42

List of Tables

Table 1: : Stakeholders and Resources overview (sec orchestration).....	13
Table 2: KPI validation Methodology (Sec orchestration).....	17
Table 3: Stakeholders and Resources Overview (Trust model)	18
Table 4: KPI validation Methodology (Trust Model)	22
Table 5: Stakeholders and Resources overview (Privacy Framework).....	23
Table 6: KPI Validation Methodology (Privacy framework)	27
Table 7: Stakeholders and Resources Overview (key generation).....	28
Table 8: KPI Validation Methodology (PKG).....	31
Table 9: Stakeholders and Resources Overview (Detection/classification of jamming attacks) 32	
Table 10: KPI Validation Methodology (Jamming attacks).....	34
Table 11: Stakeholders and Resources Overview (Security controls programming Forwarding planes).....	35
Table 12: KPI Validation Methodology (Security controls programming Forwarding planes)....	38

List of Acronyms

UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
AI	Artificial Intelligence
KPI	Key performance Indicator
FL	Federated Learning
NIF	Network Intelligence Function
ZSM	Zero touch network & Service Management
OSM	OpenSource MANO
NSD	Network Service Descriptor
NFV	Networks Function Virtualization
NFVI	Networks Function Virtualization Infrastructure
NFVO	Networks Function Virtualization Orchestrator
SBA	Service Based Architecture
LCM	LifeCycle Management
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
AC	Access Control
ZKP	Zero Knowledge Proof
DP	Differential Privacy
SMPC	Secure multi party Computation
HE	Homomorphic encryption
MANO	Management and Orchestration
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
SLA	Service Level Agreement
PET	Privacy Enhancing Technologies
PPO	Privacy preserving Orchestration
RAN	Radio Access Network
RF	Radio Frequency

Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines our blueprint for the validation approach within the 6GENABLERS-SEC project. It provides a detailed overview of the test cases, the use case, and the testbed used in our evaluation. In addition, this document details the validation methodology by defining evaluation objectives and realistic testcase scenarios. We later review the testbed platform, including infrastructure node configurations, network setup, and application deployment, aiming at replicating typical cloud continuum environments forethought to be used in the next generation of mobile network.

This deliverable eventually depicts the establishment of the testbed that will serve the evaluation of the Trust & Privacy Framework (in deliverable E6.2), of the Physical Layer Security Mechanisms (in deliverable E6.3), the Pervasive Security Framework (deliverable E6.4), and the attacking Environment Setup (E6.5).

We later proceed with the conclusions.

1. Introduction

The 6GENABLERS-SEC project seeks to ensure that future mobile networks are based on state-of-the-art security and privacy standards. An element of this goal is to create a solid security base necessary for developing trust and ensuring privacy in an interconnected digital reality predisposed to digital threats that are constantly growing [1]. Thus, the 6GENABLERS-SEC project will make sure the future wireless networks become more secure and smarter for everyone.

This document defines the basis for the validation methodology of the 6GENABLERS-SEC project, in a structured way including detailed test cases, use cases, and characteristics of the dedicated testbed. Indeed, the purpose is to describe in detail the method used to measure the components of the 6GENABLERS-SEC trust and privacy framework, security orchestration, physical layer and jamming attack detection and security Programmability at SDN. Our objective is to quantify the effectiveness of the proposed security mechanisms. This document establishes the basis for future testing procedures. It represents the initial stage in demonstrating our security and privacy measures within a real operational setting. The rapidly changing landscape of cyber threats and increasingly complex attacks necessitates a comprehensive validation strategy for holo-conferencing systems. This technology, anticipated to showcase the full capacity of 6G networks, requires thorough validation to ensure its security and privacy measures are effective and adaptable to various threats in a dynamic environment. By emphasizing rigorous testing and evaluation within the holo-conferencing context, the project seeks to establish a solid foundation for protecting user data and maintaining user trust in this advanced communication network. As outlined in deliverable E2.1, the identified KPIs (e.g., KPI X.1, KPI X.2) are utilized in this deliverable to ensure alignment with the previously established use case requirements and to provide a consistent framework for evaluating the performance and compliance of the deployed HOLOMIT application.

1.1 Target Audience

This deliverable targets a broad set of stakeholders such as security professionals, and technical teams engaged in improving 6G network security. Academic Researchers and professionals specializing in mobile and network security, and privacy will find the validation and evaluation scenarios presented in this document to be a valuable resource. These scenarios offer insight into the applied test cases and formulated scenario's, providing an understanding of practical settings for further research and analysis. The insights represented critical to people specializing in the development, deployment, and verification of security mechanisms, making upcoming 6G infrastructure resilient against new threat vectors.

1.2 Document Structure

This deliverable will be following the below structure to present the content of the document:

Introduction: This section introduces the document by outlining its purpose, objectives, and significance within the project's overall goals.

Validation Methodology, Evaluation Scenarios & Validation Stages, Evaluation Planning: This part of the presentation offers a detailed elucidation of the systematic validation approach. The following are the highlights of the section: objectives and scope that address which validation exercises should be carried out the process used in the validation, the different evaluation scenarios and evaluation stages that will help define and measure those evaluation scenarios; evaluation planning that allocates timeframes, necessary resources and the criteria for success.

Infrastructure Testbed Setup: This chapter is devoted to the practical side of the validation and describes in detail the setup of the infrastructure testbed.

Conclusion: This concluding section, referenced as Chapter 4, will recap the key points discussed throughout the document, including the validation methodology, evaluation scenarios, and the infrastructure testbed establishment.

2. Validation Methodology

The validation process for our project 6GENABLERS-SEC may be described as a set of methodologically and systematically planned steps, during which the security and privacy frameworks will be tested and validated keeping in view and align it with the KPI's of the project. This systematic approach consists of a number of stages, ending with validation and performance analysis

- First, we develop validation methodology and a performance analysis plan. This important document allows us to determine specific test cases that would simulate the complex situations our security solutions may face, and to ensure that our validation process is both effective and focused.
- In the context of our validation preparation, security and privacy tests are one of the components that we are currently developing. These tests help us to ensure that they will help our team to understand whether or not our solutions are implemented properly.
- Finally, it is proposed to implement the validation and performance analysis processes. In the scope of this final activity of the final phase, the security frameworks developed by the project will be assessed according to the original use cases and KPIs. The assessment will focus on the security, trust, and privacy properties of our use case (holo-conferencing), evaluating their effectiveness, adaptability, and performance within environments designed to replicate real-life conditions.

In order to perform this approach, we describe necessary flow steps:

- Define and refine the validation methodology and performance analysis plan to ensure alignment with project goals
- Craft the detailed test cases designed to simulate real-world security scenarios, which can grant complete coverage
- Develop prototypes in parallel with the expectations defined by the validation plan, which would ensure that the prototypes produced in the stage are the faithful representations of the proposed security and privacy solutions.
- Conduct validation tests as defined in the plan and assess performance on all use case scenarios
- Analyze how the deployment of a security solution capabilities correspond to the use case defined and how close they are to the KPIs.
- Realization of an evaluation of security and privacy functionalities to determine their consistency with the predefined KPIs and the project's objectives.
- Performance evaluation to test the efficiency and effectiveness of the selected solutions across different operational data.

2.1 Validation Objectives

The validation objectives for the 6GENABLERS-SEC project are important to achieve as they will help to ensure that the innovative security and privacy solutions developed by the project will align with the general purpose of the project. These objectives will

help to define the systematic approach taken to validate the effectiveness and efficiency of the different components developed by the project, and their capacity to secure the 6G network landscape.

- **Security & Privacy Orchestration (i2CAT):** The objective is to verify the ability to dynamically manage and enforce security and privacy policies over the network in order to constraint the behaviour of the deployment applications.
- **Identity Management and Access Control (i2CAT):** This includes testing whether inter-slice authentication mechanisms that use zero-knowledge proof work are effective for providing robust authentication and authorisation control.
- **Trust Model (UoC):** The purpose is to assess the integration of the node reputation mechanism in the Network Intelligent Function. This evaluation is supposed to confirm the potential of the framework in improving trust within the network with the help of node reputations and, therefore, ensuring the security and reliability of network functions.
- **Privacy Framework (UoC):** This involves verifying the mechanism for preserving the privacy of the Machine Learning models with the help of Federated Learning. Since AI models are becoming increasingly important for Zero-touch network & Service Management in the field of telecom, this validation aims to prove that the framework can deliver on its promise to protect the privacy of the models while ensuring the possibility of their collaborative improvement.
- **Physical Layer Key Generation (Grad):** The goal is to validate the key generation process for physical keys, ensuring they can secure communications at the physical layer. This evaluation assesses how well the generated keys maintain network integrity and confidentiality under different channel conditions. By comparing key generation in normal conditions and scenarios with signal degradation, the validation process checks if the keys meet standards for securing physical layer communications, which is important for the overall security framework.
- **Detection, Classification, and Mitigation xApps (Grad):** The evaluation of xApps implementation will test detecting, classifying, and mitigating jamming attacks in the network. Key performance indicators will be assessed to check the system's effectiveness. Tests will evaluate the use of algorithms to improve jamming detection and classification. The implementation of O-RAN architecture will also be tested, focusing on its ability to interact with the network, retrieve monitoring metrics, and execute control actions to address detected issues.

■ 2.1.1 Security & Privacy Orchestration

We contemplate Security & Privacy orchestration to leverage policy-based security and privacy management across multiple network domains, both at the edge and core, to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of highly immersive and interactive communications. As an illustration from the project use-case, the HoloMIT application is deployed with TOSCA-based security and privacy policies to ensure end-to-end protection across the cloud-to-edge continuum. The scenario's also tests Zero-Knowledge Proof-Based Authentication in HOLOMIT to secure inter-slice communication while maintaining privacy and trust. Validation evaluates authentication latency, system performance, and resilience to threats under dynamic network conditions.

This evaluation plan aims at validating the framework's ability to meet specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to security and privacy management efficiency, policy deployment latency, and the system's overall scalability and flexibility. It underscores the capability of the proposed solution to manage complex security requirements in highly immersive and interactive communications environments. Validation focuses on assessing policy enforcement, deployment latency, performance impact, authentication latency, and communication integrity under various conditions.

Stakeholders and Resources Overview

Stakeholder	Stakeholder Description	Platform Components
Application Provider	Utilizes the security framework to protect application data and ensure privacy. Offers a variety of applications that require security and privacy orchestration across different domains.	Domain Manager, Policy Engine, Policy Specification
Infrastructure Provider	Provides the physical and virtual infrastructure necessary for deploying the orchestration framework.	Local Orchestrators
End users	End users are the direct beneficiaries of the network, utilizing its services for various personal and professional communications.	Application Provider
Platform Provider	The platform provider manages and maintains the core components of the network platform, offering both technological infrastructure and application services to meet user needs	Infra. Orchestrator, Radio, Edge/Cloud

Table 1: Stakeholders and Resources overview (sec orchestration)

Scenario 1: Deploying Application with Integrated Security Policies

Objective: Deploy the complete HOLOMIT application, along with its defined security and privacy policies, as a unified TOSCA-based package. Evaluate how well the application enforces these policies during operation.

Steps:

- Define a detailed security and privacy policy for the application.
- Upload the policy and let the TOSCA-based Policy Engine to interpret the security and privacy requirement and deploying the HOLOMIT application on worker VM.
- Start a holographic communication session using the deployed application.
- During the holographic session, monitor the enforcement of security and privacy policies in real-time, ensuring compliance through system logs and alerts.

Expected Outcome:

- Policies are enforced, blocking unauthorized access with logged activity, aligning with KPI X.1.
- Security constraints remain active under stress with no performance impact, meeting KPI X.4.
- Comprehensive security coverage ensures detection and denial of unauthorized actions, satisfying KPI X.5

Scenario 2: Zero-Knowledge Proof-Based Authentication

Objective: Test the effectiveness of inter-slice authentication mechanisms using zero-knowledge proof within the deployed application to ensure secure communication.

Steps:

- Set up and manually zero-knowledge proof-based authentication on the testbed on distinct domains and ensure it functions normally and aligns with deployment requirements.
- Initiate inter-slice communication within the running HOLOMIT application
- Manually trigger authentication process using zero-knowledge proof mechanisms with legit identities, and proceed with the measurement as detailed per the method declared in the KPI table. Verify the success of the authentication.
- Introduce attempts to access slices without proper authentication or with incorrect proofs to evaluate the robustness of the mechanism by generating requests with invalid tokens and expired credentials, and proceed with the

measurement as detailed per the method declared in the KPI table. Verify that these attempts are blocked.

- Measure the time taken for authentication and ensure that no sensitive data is exposed during the process.

Expected Outcome:

- The zero-knowledge proof-based authentication should be executed efficiently, with logs and system metrics confirming the authentication process occurs within acceptable timeframes, meeting KPI X.2 (Real-Time Adjustment Efficiency) and KPI X.3 (Security Mechanism Configuration Time). Authentication events should be verified through successful session initiations and rejection of unauthorized attempts, demonstrating the process is active and effective.
- Unauthorized access attempts should be correctly rejected, and logs should confirm that the HOLOMIT application enforces authentication policies effectively, preventing unauthorized interaction with holographic sessions, aligning with KPI X.5 (Comprehensive Security and Privacy Coverage).
- The deployment should maintain seamless communication quality and prevent any performance degradation.

KPI Validation Methodology

KPI ID	Methodology
<p>KPI X.1: End-to-End Communication Delay</p>	<p>Evaluates the total time taken for communication between two distinct interlocutors across the holoconferencing testbed. This will be measured using system-level monitoring tools installed on the Master VM and Worker VMs, such as packet tracking tools, latency monitoring scripts, and time-stamped communication logs collected by Open Source MANO (OSM). The measurement process will track timestamps at key stages: the initiation of a message or data packet at the sender (Master VM or Worker VM), transmission across the network slices (via the OSM-managed infrastructure), and final receipt by the recipient. The total delay will be calculated as the difference between the timestamp of the packet's generation and its successful receipt at the destination, factoring in transmission, processing, and queuing delays.</p>
<p>KPI X.2: Security & Privacy Enforcement Configuration</p>	<p>Measures the time taken to log and successfully apply new security and privacy mechanisms within the holocommunication system for the deployment of 6G applications. The measurement process relies on system logs to capture key timestamps, including the initiation of the configuration request, its propagation through the system, and its final enforcement across the Master and Worker VMs. These logs will be collected from OpenStack telemetry tools and the Open Source</p>

KPI ID	Methodology
	<p>MANO (OSM) orchestrator to ensure accuracy. To validate the system's performance during configuration, iPerf3 will simulate holo-conferencing traffic to monitor metrics such as throughput, latency, jitter, and packet loss, ensuring that configuration actions do not degrade active communication quality.</p>
<p>KPI X.3: Bandwidth & Latency</p>	<p>Measures the maximum data transfer rate (bandwidth) and end-to-end delay (latency) in the holo-conferencing testbed, focusing on the network infrastructure's performance. Using iPerf3, generating controlled traffic between the Master VM, Worker VMs, and MANO VM. Latency is calculated as the time difference between the transmission of data packets at the sender VM and their reception at the destination VM, factoring in transmission and queuing delays. Bandwidth is evaluated as the volume of data successfully transmitted over the network within a specified timeframe. This KPI evaluates baseline network performance, independent of security or configuration actions, ensuring the testbed meets bandwidth and latency requirements for holo-conferencing.</p>
<p>KPI X.4: System Resource Optimization</p>	<p>Evaluates the efficiency of the testbed in managing computational power, memory usage, and network resource utilization during holocommunication activities. Resource metrics such as CPU load, memory consumption, and network throughput will be monitored using Prometheus with Node Exporter agents deployed on the Master, Worker, and OSM VMs. Although OpenStack's Telemetry service, Ceilometer, is considered for such tasks, its applicability will depend on the final testbed setup and tool integration feasibility. Baseline resource usage will be established under normal operation, and deviations will be analyzed during data transmission and holo-conferencing sessions to assess the system's ability to optimize resource allocation under varying workloads.</p>
<p>KPI X.5: Security & Privacy Coverage</p>	<p>Ensures that every component of the 6G holo-conferencing application deployment (Master VM, Worker VMs, and MANO VM) is safeguarded by verifying the enforcement of defined security and privacy policies. The coverage will be validated by analyzing system and policy enforcement logs from the testbed infrastructure. Key properties of the reference policies such as access control, data handling, and communication restrictions will be checked for compliance through log entries generated during operations. The validation process ensures that all infrastructure components are actively governed by the deployed policies, reducing risks and</p>

KPI ID	Methodology
	confirming comprehensive security and privacy coverage.

Table 2: KPI validation Methodology (Sec orchestration)

■ 2.1.2 Trust Model

The trust model within the 6G network architecture plays a pivotal role in ensuring the reliability and security of communication channels. By evaluating the reputation of network entities, it aims to foster end-to-end connections characterized by high-quality service delivery, robust security measures, stringent privacy protections, and minimal latency. Through the generation of global reputation scores, utilizing both direct and indirect trust values, the framework allows entities to assess and communicate their trustworthiness. A blockchain infrastructure is used to distributively store and disseminate reputation. Leveraging a blockchain infrastructure, reputation data is securely stored and distributed across the network.

The first design of the trust framework is described in “*Deliverable E3.3 First Design of the Trust and Privacy Framework*” and whose final design and implementation will be described in “*Deliverable E3.4 Final Design and Implementation of the Trust & Privacy Framework*”.

The primary goal of this initial evaluation plan is to assess the viability and security of the Trust framework in accordance with the predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) pertaining to trust modeling, management and security.

Stakeholders and Resources Overview

Stakeholder	Stakeholder Description	Tests for Platform Components
Platform Provider	Responsible for defining, implementing, and validating trust mechanisms within the architecture.	Policy Engine, Domain Manger, Security Functions and Trust Domains (Validation of the Trust Evaluation System in the application and orchestration layer. Tests include verifying the generation of global reputation scores, accurate trust computations, and blockchain-based

Stakeholder	Stakeholder Description	Tests for Platform Components
		reputation data dissemination)

Table 3: Stakeholders and Resources Overview (Trust model)

Scenario 1: Testing the Applicability of Trust Mechanisms Across Various Domains

Objective: Validate that the Trust Evaluation System establishes trust relationships across Edge and Core domains.

Steps:

- Deploy the Trust Evaluation System to compute trust across Edge and Core Trust Domains in a testbed.
- Deploy and Configure IDS and remote attestation security functions within each domain to collect performance metrics (e.g., authentication success rates, reliability scores).
- Verify that metrics from security functions send metrics to the blockchain via the Trust Evaluation System.
- Tamper one file monitored by the remote attestation engine. Verify the alert is sent to the reputation system. Revert the file to its original state.
- Start a port scanning in the domain. Verify that the IDS trigger an alert. Assess that the reputation of the domain is decreased. Stop the scanning, assess that the IDS stop emitting alerts. Verify that the reputation of the domain increases.

Expected Outcome:

- Trust relationships are successfully established across domains.
- Metrics are collected and transmitted to the blockchain for processing.
- Computed trust scores align with global policies.

Scenario 2: Testing the Efficiency of Evidence Registration and Reputation Computation

Objective: Assess the system's ability to collect evidence, send it to the blockchain, and compute reputation scores efficiently.

Steps:

- Deploy trust nodes and ensure Security Functions in each Trust Domain collect evidence from local devices.
- Security Functions transmit the evidence to the Trust Evaluation System.
- The Trust Evaluation System sends evidence to the blockchain for storage.

- Query the blockchain to compute reputation scores.
- Measure the time for each step: evidence collection, transmission to blockchain, and reputation computation.

Expected Outcome:

- Evidence is registered in non-real-time but within system-defined limits, ensuring timeliness (evidence is collected and transmitted within acceptable time frames), accuracy (data from domains/devices matches expected inputs), completeness (all required evidence is included), and integrity (evidence is securely transmitted to and stored in the blockchain).
- Reputation scores are computed in near-real-time for decision-making.
- The system meets time-efficiency goals for all steps.

Scenario 3: Testing the Scalability of the Trust System

Objective: Test the scalability of trust evidence collection and processing under a high-traffic scenario.

Steps:

- Simulate a high-density network with multiple trust nodes distributed in Edge and Core Trust Domains. In practice, create multiple administrative domains in multiple infrastructures, and deploy example network functions and security functions. Simulate traffic between different network function.
- The Trust Evaluation System processes this evidence and sends it to the blockchain.
- Query the blockchain to calculate reputation scores for all participating nodes.

Expected Outcome:

- The system handles high traffic without significant performance degradation.
- Evidence collection and reputation computations remain consistent and efficient.

Scenario 4: Evaluating the Decentralization Capabilities of the Trust System

Objective: Validate that the trust system operates effectively in a decentralized manner using blockchain for trust evidence and reputation propagation.

Steps:

- Deploy blockchain infrastructure to support decentralized evidence collection and reputation propagation.
- Security Functions in each Trust Domain collect metrics independently and transmit them to the Trust Evaluation System.

- Trust Evaluation System sends data to blockchain without relying on centralized coordination.
- Verify that reputation scores can be calculated and retrieved by nodes across domains.

Expected Outcome:

- Evidence and reputation data are distributed securely via blockchain.
- Decentralized operation ensures no single point of failure.
- Trust computations are consistent across nodes in different domains.

KPI Validation Methodology

The KPI that will be validated for the Trust framework are included in “Deliverable E3.3 First Design of the Trust and Privacy Framework” in “Section 2.1 Updated version of the Trust Requirements and KPIs”, more specifically in “Table 2 Updated Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for the trust framework”. The final version of the KPI will be included in “Deliverable E3.4 Final Design and Implementation of the Trust & Privacy Framework”. The current KPI are shown below.

KPI ID	Methodology
<p>KPI T-1: Multidimensional trust information collection</p>	<p>Each of these trust nodes will analyze its connections (incoming and outgoing packets) and generate evidences locally with respect to its direct peer trust nodes. Depending on the metric evaluated (e.g., latency, bandwidth, etc), trust nodes may also execute performance tests against their peers (e.g., speed tests, pings, etc).</p>
<p>KPI T-2: Cross-domain end-to-end trust establishment</p>	<p>Validation will be performed between trust nodes belonging to different trust domains (or entities/operators) connected to the same DLT network. The process for trust establishment across multiple domains is as follows: Trust nodes in each domain will generate performance evidence and record it on the DLT network, making it accessible to all participating trust nodes. Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and trust policies (thresholds) established by each domain will also be stored on the DLT to ensure transparency and uniform reference points. Trust nodes will query the DLT to access both the generated evidences and SLAs from other domains. Using this data, trust nodes will calculate and validate reputation scores for other nodes, independently of the trust domain to which they belong. Trust will be established between trust nodes based on these reputation scores and the thresholds defined in the policies of each trust domain.</p>

KPI ID	Methodology
KPI T-3: Efficiency	Specifically, it will be analyzed the time required for evidence generation and recording in the DLT, where each trust node collects performance data (e.g., SLA compliance, reliability metrics) and securely submits it to the DLT for storage (in non-real time), and query evidences generated by other trust nodes and calculation and validation of reputation scores (in near-real time).
KPI T-4: Scalability	Here, it will be analyzed the time required for evidence generation and recording in the DLT, where each trust node collects performance data (e.g., SLA compliance, reliability metrics) and securely submits it to the DLT for storage (in non-real time), and query evidences generated by other trust nodes and calculation and validation of reputation scores (in near-real time).
KPI T-5: Decentralization	It will be validated that the trust nodes are able to share their evidences with integrity and that the evidences and reputation scores of the other trust nodes are available for validation. The integrity of evidence sharing can be verified in practice by ensuring that all evidence data shared by the trust nodes is cryptographically signed before submission to the DLT. The signatures are validated upon retrieval from the DLT to confirm that the data has not been tampered with. Additionally, hash comparisons of evidence records before and after submission to the DLT can be performed to ensure data integrity during storage and transmission.
KPI T-6: Effectivity	Different risks related to trust and reputation scores will be evaluated. Sybil attacks will be carried out on the testbed to demonstrate that a single entity is not capable of significantly influencing trust scores. To achieve this, the malicious trust node will create multiple wallets and submit fake evidences to the blockchain, simulating a Sybil attack. Measurable metrics will include the number of fake evidences detected by the system, the impact on trust scores of legitimate nodes, and the overall deviation in the global reputation scores. The subjectivity problem and collusion attacks will also be evaluated to prove that they are prevented in the most prominent cases. For collusion, malicious nodes will exchange and validate fake evidences to artificially inflate their scores, and measurable outcomes will include the detection of abnormal score patterns and the system's ability to maintain the integrity of trust scores despite collusion attempts.

KPI ID	Methodology
KPI T-7: Ubiquitous and private identities	It will be validated that trust nodes can register in the system and that they can resolve other identities in near real-time using the decentralized registry implemented in the smart contracts. This can be verified in practice by examining the logs generated during the registration and resolution processes, ensuring successful interactions with the smart contracts. Key metrics to measure include the time taken for registration, the latency in resolving identifiers for other trust nodes, and the success rate of name resolution requests. Additional validation can include querying the DLT to ensure the correct mapping of identifiers to pseudo-anonymous addresses and verifying consistency across the system during simultaneous resolution requests from nodes in different locations.
KPI T-8: DLT Deployment	This measures the ability of each component to successfully interact with the DLT through their wallets, including performing transactions and retrieving data. The metrics evaluated include the success rate of these interactions, the latency for transaction completion or data retrieval, and the overall reliability of the DLT in handling requests from diverse infrastructure components.
KPI T-9: Reputation scores	The focus will be on measuring whether the smart contracts function as expected by accurately recording performance evidence, calculating reputation scores correctly, and making global trust scores available in a reliable manner. Key metrics include the accuracy of the data stored on the DLT, the efficiency of querying and retrieving trust scores, and the time taken from evidence submission to trust score updates. This ensures that the smart contracts are effectively managing trust-related data and supporting the overall system functionality.

Table 4: KPI validation Methodology (Trust Model)

■ 2.1.3 Privacy Framework

The privacy framework is a comprehensive defense mechanism designed to counteract potential privacy threats. Its primary function is to prevent the extraction of sensitive information from data collected within the network. The framework enhances the resilience of AI models in network management, protecting them against security and privacy attacks. Scenarios are designed to test its ability to safeguard core cloud infrastructure and AI models from data breaches and adversarial threats.

The first design of the privacy framework is described in “*Deliverable E3.3 First Design of the Trust and Privacy Framework*” and whose final design and implementation will be described in “*Deliverable E3.4 Final Design and Implementation of the Trust & Privacy Framework*”.

The primary goal of this initial evaluation plan is to assess the effectiveness of the Privacy mechanisms in accordance with the predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) pertaining privacy, with a specific focus on usability.

Stakeholders and Resources Overview

Stakeholder	Stakeholder Description	Roles	Tests for Platform Components
Platform Provider	Protects sensitive data collected and processed across the 5G/6G network, ensuring compliance with privacy policies.	Application Provider, Platform Provider, Infra structure Provider	-Trust Domains (Edge and Core): Collects and processes local data. - Local Orchestrator: Ensures service consistency and inter-domain coordination. - Security Functions: Implements protection mechanisms for privacy and trust data. and Core data collectors

Table 5: Stakeholders and Resources overview (Privacy Framework)

Scenario 1: Assess the Delay Introduced by Privacy Mechanisms

Objective: To measure the impact of privacy mechanisms on system delay and ensure protection without compromising performance.

Steps:

- Configure privacy mechanisms (e.g., encryption, pseudonymization) in the Security Functions for both Edge and Core Trust Domains.
- Simulate end-to-end communication between two devices located in different Trust Domains, monitored by the Domain Manager.
- Measure the communication latency at various points in the network flow, including during data collection and transmission across the domains.
- Compare results against baseline communication without privacy mechanisms.

Expected Outcome:

- End-to-end delay remains below defined thresholds for near-real-time and non-real-time applications.
- Privacy mechanisms introduce acceptable additional latency without disrupting critical network operations.

Scenario 2: Assess the Time Taken to Configure Privacy Mechanisms

Objective: To evaluate the time required to configure privacy mechanisms and ensure efficient implementation without delaying system deployment.

Steps:

- Deploy new privacy mechanisms (e.g., encryption algorithms, noise injection policies) via the Policy Engine.
- Measure the configuration and activation time of the privacy mechanisms across the Security Functions in both Edge and Core Trust Domains.
- Monitor for any delays or disruptions caused during active network operations.

Expected Outcome:

- Privacy mechanisms should be configured and active within less than 30 seconds for small-scale updates.
- The configuration process should not disrupt ongoing data flows or affect real-time network functions.

Scenario 3: Assess Added Delay and Transfer Rate with Noise Injection

Objective: To assess the impact of noise injection on system delay and data transfer rate, ensuring security enhancements do not significantly degrade performance.

Steps:

- Enable noise injection as a privacy mechanism in the Security Functions during inter-domain communication.
- Measure maximum data transfer rates and latency during communication between devices in different Trust Domains.
- Evaluate performance under varying noise levels (e.g., low, medium, high) and analyze the trade-off between privacy level and performance metrics.

Expected Outcome:

- Maximum data transfer rate should remain within 90% of baseline rates for critical applications.
- Latency added due to noise injection should remain below 10ms for real-time communication.

Scenario 4: Evaluate the Trade-offs of Privacy Mechanisms

Objective: To analyze the trade-offs between the security provided by privacy mechanisms and their impact on system performance and efficiency.

Steps :

- Implement privacy mechanisms (e.g., differential privacy, encryption) in the **Security Functions** across Edge and Core Trust Domains.
- Measure system resource usage (CPU, memory, and storage) during data collection and inter-domain communication.
- Adjust the parameters of the privacy mechanisms (e.g., encryption strength, noise level) to evaluate resource trade-offs.
- Analyze the impact on system performance under varying privacy mechanism settings.

Expected Outcome:

- CPU utilization remains below 70%, memory usage below 80%, and storage remains scalable for 5G/6G workloads.
- System performance remains stable and functional under varying privacy parameters.

Scenario 5: Assess Privacy Mechanism Coverage

Objective: To evaluate the extent and effectiveness of privacy mechanisms in addressing potential security and privacy vulnerabilities across the system.

Steps:

- Identify critical components in the architecture, including Domain Manager, Security Functions, and Trust Domains.
- Map privacy mechanisms (e.g., encryption, pseudonymization) to each critical component.
- Simulate scenarios where privacy mechanisms are tested for effectiveness during data exchange and processing.
- Identify any components lacking privacy protection mechanisms.

Expected Outcome:

- All critical components are protected by at least one privacy mechanism.
- Any gaps in privacy coverage are identified and addressed during the evaluation.

Scenario 6: Execute Privacy Attacks to Create Datasets for Training Models

Objective: To perform privacy attacks and generate datasets for training models, enabling improved detection and mitigation of similar threats in the future.

Steps:

- Simulate privacy attacks (e.g., model inversion, membership inference, data leakage) on data flows between Edge and Core Trust Domains.
- Use the Security Functions to monitor and log these attacks, categorizing their scope and impact.
- Create datasets of the attack scenarios, capturing details of vulnerabilities and their effects.
- Use these datasets for offline analysis and AI model training to strengthen privacy frameworks.

Expected Outcome:

- Comprehensive datasets of simulated attacks are created, categorized by type, impact, and severity.
- Insights are gained on improving privacy mechanisms to prevent such attacks in real-world deployments.

KPI Validation Methodology

The KPI that will be validated for the Privacy framework are included in “*Deliverable E3.3 First Design of the Trust and Privacy Framework*” in “*Section 2.2 Updated version of the Privacy Requirements*”, more specifically in “*Table 2 Updated Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for the privacy framework*”. The final version of the KPI will be included in “*Deliverable E3.4 Final Design and Implementation of the Trust & Privacy Framework*”. The current KPI are shown below.

KPI ID	Methodology
KPI P-1: End-to-End Communication Delay	A testbed infrastructure that includes clients (mobiles, tablets and laptops) and a 6G infrastructure composed of RAN, Transport and Core components distributed in the edge and cloud. End-to-end delay in the communication between two distinct clients should be less than equal to 50ms
KPI P-2: Security & privacy enforcement configuration	Configuration of the security and privacy mechanisms on the testbed infrastructure that will include 6G clients such as smartphones, AR/VR headsets, holographic projection devices supporting holo-conferencing applications, and a 6G infrastructure composed of RAN, Transport, and Core components distributed in the edge and cloud.
KPI P-3: Bandwidth & Latency	Inject controlled random noise to data generated by the testbed infrastructure that will include 6G clients (mobiles, tablets and laptops) and a representative composed of RAN, Transport and Core components distributed in the edge and cloud. Measure the added bandwidth and latency in relation to the amount of noise injected.

KPI ID	Methodology
KPI P-4: System Resource Optimization	Inject controlled random noise to data generated by the testbed infrastructure that will include 6G clients (mobiles, tablets and laptops) and a 6G infrastructure composed of RAN, Transport and Core components distributed in the edge and cloud. Measure the relation between the computational power, memory usage, and storage utilization and the amount of noise injected.
KPI P-5: Security & Privacy Coverage	Set up a testbed infrastructure that will include 6G clients (mobiles, tablets, laptops, AR/VR devices, and IoT sensors) and a 6G infrastructure composed of RAN, Transport, and Core components distributed in the edge and cloud. Identify the most critical components of a holo-conferencing application deployment, such as holographic projection devices, real-time AR/VR data streams, and edge computing nodes, and confirm that they are safeguarded by at least one element of the security and privacy mechanisms in place, such as encryption, pseudonymization, and noise injection.
KPI P-6: Datasets	Set up a testbed infrastructure that will include 6G clients (mobiles, tablets, laptops, AR/VR headsets, and holographic conferencing equipment) and a 6G infrastructure composed of RAN, Transport, and Core components distributed in the edge and cloud. Obtain data from the testbed during holo-conferencing sessions, execute privacy attacks (e.g., inference attacks on holographic data streams), and train AI models to detect such attacks. Measure the classification accuracy of these models in identifying and mitigating privacy threats specific to holo-conferencing use cases.
KPI P-7: Privacy settings	From the datasets obtained in KPI-P06, define metrics to evaluate utility, privacy, latency, and sustainability. Metrics will include end-to-end latency, privacy loss index, and energy consumption to assess the impact and efficiency of the privacy mechanisms. These will form part of the test methodology.

Table 6: KPI Validation Methodology (Privacy framework)

■ 2.1.4 Physical Layer Key Generation

The Physical Layer Key Generation mechanisms being designed and developed will provide a method for enhancing private key generation methods based on the PKG paradigm. This paradigm leverages the wireless channel shared information between two nodes to generate the information required to generate a key following a process of well-defined steps. Therefore, the technical component that we aim to validate is the Physical Layer Key Generation mechanisms, whose initial design is described in

“Deliverable E4.2: First Design of the Security Mechanisms in the Physical Layer” and whose final design and implementation will be described in “Deliverable E4.3 Final Design and Implementation of the Security Mechanisms in the Physical Layer”.

This initial version of the evaluation plan aims at assessing the ability of Physical Layer Key Generation mechanisms to meet specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to security and privacy, more specifically communications eavesdropping prevention. The scenario tests the robustness of Physical Layer Key Generation (PLKG) mechanisms against passive eavesdropping, active jamming, man-in-the-middle, and replay attacks. Validation involves simulating these attacks to evaluate the system’s ability to generate secure keys under adversarial conditions.

Stakeholders and Resources Overview

Stakeholder	Stakeholder Description	Tests for Platform Components
Infrastructure Provider	Utilizes the generated private key to prevent eavesdropping in end-to-end communications links	Physical Layer Key Generation mechanisms

Table 7: Stakeholders and Resources Overview (key generation)

Scenario 1: Eavesdropping prevention in Wireless Communication environment

- **Objective:** To assess the improvement of deploying PKG-based mechanisms in two example communications nodes in a wireless channel to decrease eavesdropping risk.

Sub Scenario 1: Secure Connection with PKG-Based Private Key

Steps:

- Implement PKG-based private key generation.
- Establish an encrypted connection between two nodes.
- Test communication for end-to-end security.

Expected Outcome:

- A secure connection is established, reducing the probability of eavesdropping risk.

Sub Scenario 2: Generating 128-Bit Key for AES Encryption

Steps:

- Configure PKG mechanisms to generate a 128-bit private key.
- Validate the key length and compatibility with AES128 encryption.

Expected Outcome:

- A 128-bit key is successfully generated for AES128 encryption.

Sub Scenario 3: Key Randomness Evaluation with NIST Standards**Steps:**

- Generate multiple keys using the PKG mechanism.
- Run the NIST random test suite on the generated keys.
- Verify that the P-value is greater than 0.01 for optimal randomness.

Expected Outcome:

- The keys meet NIST random test suite standards with a P-value greater than 0.01.

Sub Scenario 4: Key Disagreement Rate (KDR) Evaluation**Steps:**

- Test key generation under different Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) conditions.
- Measure the Key Disagreement Rate between the two nodes.
- Analyze KDR to ensure it remains below the threshold of 1%.

Expected Outcome:

- KDR is less than 1%, indicating minimal discrepancies between the nodes.

Sub Scenario 5: Key Generation Rate (KGR) Assessment**Steps:**

- Simulate various channel scenarios using the QuaDRiGa channel emulator.
- Measure the Key Generation Rate under different channel qualities.
- Ensure the KGR increases proportionally to the observed quality and extracted information.

Expected Outcome:

- The KGR increases proportionally with channel quality and extracted information, reaching optimal thresholds.

KPI Validation Methodology

The KPI that will be validated for the said Physical Layer Key Generation mechanism are included in “*Deliverable E2.4: System Requirements for the Physical Layer v1.0*” in “*Section 6.2 Key Generation*”, more specifically in “*Table 4 Key Generation KPIs*”. The final version of the KPI will be included in “*Deliverable E4.3 Final Design and Implementation of the Security Mechanisms in the Physical Layer*”. The current KPI are shown below.

KPI ID	Methodology
KPI PKG-10: Guarantee a secure connection	Set up a laboratory testbed with two communication nodes and establish a test wireless communications link between them that used the generated private key. The security of the connection between two terminals should be measured through the ability to reduce eavesdropping probability by a third communications node acting as an eavesdropper. This can be achieved using PKG based on temporal variation, channel reciprocity, and spatial decorrelation of electromagnetic waves, ensuring keys are dynamic, derived independently by legitimate nodes, and unusable by an eavesdropper in a different location.
KPI PKG-20: Key Generation length	Set up a laboratory testbed with one User Terminal and one Base Station both implementing the PKG-based security mechanism in a mobility scenario and measure the length in bits of the private key that is generated by both of them.
KPI PKG-30: NIST random test	Set up a laboratory testbed with one User Terminal and one Base Station both implementing the PKG-based security mechanism in a mobility scenario and apply the private key that is generated to the NIST random test suite to assess whether it meets the NIST standards with a P-value greater than 0.01 for optimal randomness.
KPI PKG-40: Key Disagreement Rate	Set up a laboratory testbed with one User Terminal and one Base Station, both implementing the PKG-based security mechanism in a mobility scenario with different SNR levels and measure the KDR, influenced by SNR, representing key discrepancies between two nodes for the different scenarios.

KPI ID	Methodology
KPI PKG-50: Key Generation Rate	Set up a laboratory testbed with one User Terminal and one Base Station, both implementing the PKG-based security mechanism in a mobility scenario with different levels of observed quality and extracted information from the physical layer and measure that KGR should increase proportionally, up to an optimal threshold.

Table 8: KPI Validation Methodology (PKG)

It should be noted that the complete final test plan to validate the KPI will be included in “*Deliverable E6.3: Platform Setup and Validation for the Secure Physical Layer*”, the document where the entire Physical Layer Key Generation mechanisms validation process is due to be reported.

■ **2.1.5 Detection, Classification, and Mitigation xApps**

The detection, classification, and mitigation xApps being designed and developed will provide a method for enhancing next-generation wireless networks security in the event of physical layer anomalies. More specifically, the focus is on detecting, classifying and mitigating jamming attacks in cellular networks that follow an Open RAN [8] architecture. Therefore, the technical components that we aim to validate are the detection, characterization, and mitigation security mechanisms for the physical layer of Open RAN networks, whose initial design is described in “*Deliverable E4.2: First Design of the Security Mechanisms in the Physical Layer*” and whose final design and implementation will be described in “*Deliverable E4.3 Final Design and Implementation of the Security Mechanisms in the Physical Layer*”.

This initial version of the evaluation plan aims at assessing the ability of the detection, characterization, and mitigation security mechanisms, more specifically for wireless communications jamming anomaly detection, classification and eventually mitigation. The scenario evaluates the detection, characterization, and mitigation mechanisms in Open RAN-based cellular networks against physical attacks, including simulated jamming. Validation involves deploying the mechanisms in a testbed, simulating attacks, and assessing their effectiveness in securing the network.

Stakeholders and Resources Overview

Stakeholder	Stakeholder Description	Tests for Platform Components
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Stakeholder	Stakeholder Description	Tests for Platform Components
Infrastructure Provider	Utilizes the detection, characterization, and mitigation algorithms to enhance network security in the event of a jamming attack that would compromise the network	Detection, characterization, and mitigation security mechanisms
Platform Provider	Implements the detection, characterization, and mitigation algorithms as xApps in their RIC platform that can be provided as a solution/product for Telecommunications Operators that implement an Open RAN architecture	Detection, characterization, and mitigation security mechanisms

Table 9: Stakeholders and Resources Overview (Detection/classification of jamming attacks)

Scenario 1: Anomaly Detection in an Open RAN Communications Environment

Objective: To assess the capability of the detection security mechanism to detect anomaly events based on signal quality and/or performance metrics obtained from an E2 node (O-RAN gNB).

Steps:

- Deploy the anomaly detection xApp in the Open RAN mobile network testbed.
- Simulate a jammer to generate jamming signals with specific J/S power ratios.
- Use detection data as an input for the classification mechanism.

Expected Outcome:

- The detection mechanism identifies anomaly events with at least 85% probability for jamming signals with a bandwidth of 5 MHz and a power level 10 dB above legitimate signals.

Scenario 2: Jamming Characterization in an Open RAN Communications Environment

Objective: To assess the capability of the characterization security mechanism to classify jamming events based on signal quality and/or performance metrics obtained

from an E2 node (O-RAN gNB) and anomaly notifications sent by the detection mechanism.

Steps:

- Run the jamming characterization xApp in the Open RAN mobile network testbed.
- Simulate various types of jamming signals (point, continuous, periodic, localized, extended, narrowband, wideband).
- Use anomaly detection outputs to feed into the characterization mechanism.

Expected Outcome:

The classification mechanism achieves:

- Supervised Method: Average accuracy of at least 85%.
- Unsupervised Method: Silhouette Score greater than 0.55.

Scenario 3: Anomaly Mitigation in an Open RAN Communications Environment

Objective: To assess the capability of the mitigation security mechanism to reduce the impact of a jamming anomaly detected by the detection mechanism and classified/notified by the characterization mechanism.

Steps:

- Deploy the anomaly mitigation xApp in the Open RAN mobile network testbed.
- Simulate a jammer to trigger jamming anomalies in the testbed network.
- Measure the mitigation response time and impact reduction on communication.

Expected Outcome:

- The mitigation mechanism reduces the impact of jamming on communication between the UE and gNBs within 5 seconds of detecting the attack.

KPI Validation Methodology

The initial version of the KPI that will be validated for the said detection, classification and mitigation mechanisms is included in *“Deliverable E2.4: System Requirements for the Physical Layer v1.0”* in *“Section 6.1 Detection, characterization and mitigation strategies against cybernetic attacks in the physical layer of 6G networks”*, more specifically in *“Table 3 Detection, mitigation and characterization KPIs”*. An updated version was reported in *“Deliverable E4.2: First Design of the Security Mechanisms in the Physical Layer”* in *“Section 2.2 KPI updates”*. The final version of the KPI will be included in *“Deliverable E4.3 Final Design and Implementation of the Security Mechanisms in the Physical Layer”*. The current KPI are shown below.

KPI ID	Methodology
KPI KOR-10: Jamming detection	Set up a laboratory testbed with one UE, two E2 nodes, one near-RT RIC, one core network and one jammer. The interference anomaly probability detection with specific Jamming to Signal (J/S) ratios will be measured in a series of runs, being a false positive the times when jamming is present and an anomaly is detected and a false negative the times when jamming is present and an anomaly is not detected. The expected probability of interference detection with a bandwidth of at least 5MHz should be higher than 85%, for interfering signals with a power level 10dB above that of legitimate signals.
KPI KOR-20: Jamming classification	Set up a laboratory testbed with one UE, two E2 nodes, one near-RT RIC, one core network and one jammer. The interference accuracy will be measured in a series of runs for each of the following types of jamming: point/continuous/periodic, localized/extended/narrowband/wideband. The classification could be based on supervised or unsupervised machine learning methods and different criteria is applicable for each of them: An Expected Average accuracy better than 85% if the selected method is supervised or Silhouette Score better than 0.55 if the selected method is unsupervised.
KPI KOR-30: Jamming Effect Review	Set up a laboratory testbed with one UE, two E2 nodes, one near-RT RIC, one core network and one jammer. When jamming is present, the time elapsed since the start of the attack until the jamming impact is reduced will be measured in seconds with an expected less than 5 seconds for the mitigation actions to take place.

Table 10: KPI Validation Methodology (Jamming attacks)

It should be noted that the final test plan to validate the KPI will be included in “*Deliverable E6.3: Platform Setup and Validation for the Secure Physical Layer*”, the document where the entire detection, classification, and mitigation security mechanisms validation process is due to be reported.

■ 2.1.6 Security Controls for Programmable Forwarding Planes

This test validates the security and performance of a network of programmable forwarding planes (e.g., SDN-enabled switches), which are controlled dynamically using P4 APIs. The test ensures robust security mechanisms such as encryption, authentication, and AI/ML-based anomaly detection systems to mitigate risks like unauthorized access, packet tampering, rule injection, and DoS attacks. The dynamic network adaptability and performance are evaluated through simulated attack scenarios, performance benchmarking, and adaptive testing in a controlled testbed.

Stakeholders and Resources Overview

Stakeholder	Stakeholder Description	Tests for Platform Components
Infrastructure Provider	Manages the deployment and maintenance of programmable forwarding planes to ensure secure and efficient network operations.	Detection, validation, and resilience mechanisms for programmable network security and performance.
Platform Provider	Ensures that programmable network components (e.g., SDN-enabled switches, P4 APIs) are secure, scalable, and dynamically adaptable.	Detection, validation, and mitigation mechanisms for unauthorized access, rule injection, and DoS attacks.

Table 11: Stakeholders and Resources Overview (Security controls programming Forwarding planes)

Scenario 1: Packet Tampering

Objective: To evaluate the system's ability to detect, mitigate, and log attempts to tamper with packet headers, payloads, or metadata. This scenario ensures the integrity and authenticity of network traffic by testing mechanisms like checksum validation, encryption, and packet signature verification.

Steps:

- Introduce tampered packets into the testbed network using a traffic generator.
- Monitor programmable switches for detection of tampered packets.
- Assess the system's ability to block these packets from reaching their destinations.

Expected Outcome:

- Tampered packets are detected and blocked effectively by programmable switches.
- Detection rate for tampered packets exceeds 95%.

Scenario 2: Rule Injection

Objective: To assess the resilience of the system against unauthorized or malicious injection of forwarding rules into the programmable forwarding plane. The test verifies

the effectiveness of access control mechanisms, rule validation processes, and monitoring for anomalous updates to the rule table.

Steps:

- Attempt to inject unauthorized forwarding rules through compromised P4 APIs.
- Test the validation mechanisms in identifying and rejecting the injected rules.
- Verify the operational integrity of the network after rejection.

Expected Outcome:

- Unauthorized rule modifications are detected and blocked with a 100% success rate.
- No disruption to legitimate traffic or forwarding rules.

Scenario 3: Denial of Service (DoS)

Objective: To examine the system's capacity to prevent, detect, and respond to DoS attacks targeting the forwarding plane. This includes testing the system's ability to maintain availability and performance under high traffic volumes or resource exhaustion attempts, such as flooding attacks.

Steps:

- Generate high traffic volumes using traffic generators to simulate a DoS attack.
- Monitor programmable devices for performance degradation and response mechanisms.
- Evaluate the system's ability to maintain legitimate traffic throughput under attack conditions.

Expected Outcome:

- System maintains legitimate traffic throughput with minimal degradation (resilience rate $\geq 90\%$).
- Programmable devices resist overload and continue secure operations.

Scenario 4: Adaptive Testing

Objective: To validate the system's adaptability to evolving threats by dynamically simulating complex attack scenarios that combine multiple vectors (e.g., packet tampering and rule injection). This ensures the robustness and flexibility of security controls and their ability to operate under real-world threat conditions.

Steps:

- Dynamically add or remove programmable devices from the testbed network.
- Simulate changes in traffic patterns and topology adjustments.
- Monitor the system's ability to adapt while maintaining security and performance.

Expected Outcome:

- The system dynamically adapts to changes without any compromise in security.
- Latency impact remains $\leq 5\%$, and throughput is maintained at $\geq 90\%$ baseline capacity.

KPI Validation Methodology

The following table outlines the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) designed to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the programmable forwarding plane security mechanisms. Each KPI focuses on a specific aspect of the system, such as performance, resilience, scalability, and security coverage. These KPIs ensure that the implemented solutions meet the desired objectives of secure, scalable, and adaptable network operations.

KPI ID	Methodology
<p>KPI T-1 Latency Impact</p>	<p>Set up a testbed with programmable forwarding planes, including SDN-enabled switches, routers, and a centralized P4 controller. Use tools such as Wireshark or iPerf to measure additional latency introduced by encryption and rule validation mechanisms during traffic transmission.</p>
<p>KPI T-2 Throughput Impact</p>	<p>Utilize traffic generators like Ostinato or Trex Traffic Generator to send varying volumes of legitimate and malicious traffic. Measure the reduction in throughput caused by active security controls such as rate-limiting and anomaly detection.</p>
<p>KPI T3 Rule Validation Rate</p>	<p>Simulate rule injection attacks using custom scripts or frameworks leveraging P4 APIs to attempt unauthorized rule modifications. Measure the percentage of blocked and detected modifications using logging tools like Elastic Stack or Splunk.</p>

KPI ID	Methodology
KPI T-4 Resilience Rate	Generate high traffic volumes simulating a DoS attack using tools like LOIC (Low Orbit Ion Cannon) or Hping3. Measure the system's ability to maintain legitimate traffic throughput under attack using iPerf or NetFlow Analyzer.
KPI T-5 Scalability	Gradually increase the number of programmable devices and traffic volume using tools such as Mininet (for emulating SDN networks) and iPerf (for traffic simulation). Monitor system performance metrics, including latency and throughput, using centralized monitoring tools like Nagios or Zabbix

Table 12: KPI Validation Methodology (Security controls programming Forwarding planes)

2.2 Evaluation Planning

Figure 1: Gantt chart

The Gantt chart illustrates a project timeline from October to December 2024, covering key phases: Security and Privacy Orchestration, Trust Model, Privacy Framework, Key Generation, xApps Development, and Security Controls Deployment. Tasks are aligned to ensure all components are evaluated and integrated by the end of December.

3. Infrastructure Testbed Setup

This section outlines the establishment of our infrastructure testbed, a critical element in our development and validation processes. The following subsections detail the testbed's objectives, its core components, and the specifics of application deployments. These elements collectively ensure a comprehensive and controlled environment for validating our design approach of Architecture and performance metrics on designated use case.

3.1 Introduction

The validation of the 6GENABLERS-SEC project's security and privacy approach towards 6G relies on the establishment of an Infrastructure federated testbed. This section presents an overview of the testbed, detailing its implementation and significance. A federated testbed is designed, which integrates diverse experimental environments and systems to replicate complex, distributed scenarios anticipated in future 6G networks. This collaborative infrastructure enables comprehensive evaluation of security and privacy measures across interconnected platforms, simulating the intricate dynamics of emerging network architectures. The subsequent subsections will cover the specific objectives, essential components, and procedures for application deployments, highlighting the critical role of this infrastructure in supporting advancements in 6G technology while prioritizing security and privacy.

3.1.1 Overview of Testbed Infrastructure

The proposed testbed infrastructure is a designed environment constructed for the purposes of simulating testing and validating the security and privacy components of the project.

The controlled, reliable, and repeatable testing conditions offered by this testbed will be used to test the security and privacy mechanisms using different types of holographic communications. The testbed will be equipped with various network functions, security tools, and orchestrating capabilities custom-designed to meet the unique needs of a 6G safe network.

3.1.2 Objectives and Design Criteria

A) Objectives

Below are the listed objectives, which will guide the project's development and ensure that the design aligns with our key goals.

I) Realistic environment simulation

The federated testbed replicates the complex dynamics of future 6G networks by incorporating a structure that unifies various network nodes, from edge to core, within a cohesive virtualized environment. This configuration allows for the effective deployment of our holo-conferencing application use case across different network segments. Through this approach, we conduct comprehensive testing of the security and privacy mechanisms designed for our application, verifying their efficacy under diverse and

realistically complex network conditions. This validation method is essential, as it confirms the resilience and adaptability of our security frameworks in scenarios closely resembling real-world applications, thereby yielding reliable and actionable data for further refinement.

II) Testbed Requirements and Specifications:

- **Cloud-Edge Integration:**

Requirement: The testbed must provide seamless integration across cloud and edge environments to reflect real-time, distributed scenarios.

Specification: A federated architecture allowing connectivity between cloud servers and edge nodes, supporting the deployment of policies and security mechanisms across this continuum. It should include dynamic resource allocation and workload distribution capabilities to mirror real-world cloud-edge network conditions.

- **Real-time Threat Simulation and Validation:**

Requirement: The testbed must support the simulation of a wide range of security threats (e.g., physical layer attacks, access control violations, P4-based attacks).

Specification: Incorporate modules that allow for real-time injection of diverse threat scenarios, including attacks on access control and switching layers, while validating the effectiveness of security measures. This can be achieved through a virtualized network environment capable of mimicking real-time attack patterns and analyzing security responses.

- **Interoperability with External Validation Tools:**

Requirement: The testbed should allow integration with advanced security and privacy monitoring tools for KPI measurement.

Specification: Open interfaces and APIs that support the integration of external monitoring, analytics, and KPI measurement tools for evaluating the performance of security mechanisms. This ensures continuous validation of trust, privacy, and security metrics within the federated testbed.

3.2 Testbed Infrastructure Components

The infrastructure of the testbed is designed in such a way as to ensure the most comprehensive validation of privacy and security aspects for the 6GENABLERS-SEC project. It comprises a variety of software and hardware components that are assembled together to replicate the elements of the network environment in the future. Below, the main items and their representations inside the testbed are described below:

3.2.1 Computing Nodes

The compute nodes, which are made up of actual servers entrusted with managing Network Functions (NFs) and guaranteeing the operational integrity of the network, are the fundamental component of our testbed architecture.

- **Master VM**

The Master Node VM operates within the Application and Security Orchestration Layer and is responsible for managing and controlling the orchestration of tasks and policies across the testbed. It serves as the main control unit for managing Kubernetes clusters, ensuring that the 6G network simulation runs efficiently. The Master Node VM manages the deployment and scheduling of the use case application components, such as HoloMIT XR Processing, Media Assets MCU, and Session Orchestrator, on the Worker Node VMs. The deployment of the HoloMIT application itself should also be covered, ensuring that the application is properly configured and operational within the testbed environment. It coordinates security and privacy mechanisms by deploying the required pods, monitoring resource utilization, and ensuring the application of security and privacy rules according to the established policies. It interacts with the OSM VM for network orchestration tasks to maintain smooth communication and data flow.

- **Worker VM**

The Worker Node VMs are part of the Local Control Layer and function as Kubernetes worker nodes within the testbed environment, running on OpenStack. They execute the computational tasks assigned by the Master Node VM and host the actual application components, such as the HoloMIT XR Processing Downlink/Uplink, HoloMIT Media Assets MCU, and Session Orchestrator. These VMs are equipped with the necessary processing power, memory, and storage to handle the intensive workloads characteristic of 6G network simulations. They are configured to ensure efficient resource usage, maintain low latency, and provide balanced network throughput, thus optimizing the performance of the overall system. The Worker Node VMs enforce the security and privacy policies as directed by the Master Node VM and interact with the OSM VM for network service management.

3.2.2 Network Interconnection

The testbed's network interconnection allows for smooth data flow and interaction between all components. High-speed switches, routers, and radio units provide both wired and wireless communication. For secure access, we connect to the OpenStack VMs using SSH over the FortiClient VPN, ensuring encrypted communication. The use of VPN technology is essential for maintaining secure data transfer and privacy, especially for applications requiring remote access and secure communications across different sites or cloud services.

The following diagram provides a visual representation of the testbed infrastructure, showcasing the computing nodes and network interconnections as previously described.

Figure 2: Testbed Components

3.2.3 Technological Foundation

- Software-Defined Networking and Network Function Virtualization

SDN introduces a level of flexibility with respect to network management. Resources can be dynamically allocated and traffic can be routed in response to current requirements. NFV, on the other hand, presents a novel way of network function deployment. The majority of network functions can now be accomplished on demand and maintained over the top of virtual machines. This puts away the requirement of holding specialized hardware for implementing network functions and thus significantly reduces operational costs.

- Container Orchestration with Kubernetes

Kubernetes serves as a leading tool in the realm of container management. It ensures that a particular network function enclosed within a container is stationed and controlled in an optimal manner. Furthermore, the orchestration capacities of Kubernetes perform in conjunction with Open Source MANO [9] to maintain the management environment for Network Services and Virtual

Network Functions. In addition, the employment over bare-metal infrastructure allows for full exploitation of available computational power without the burden of virtualization layers that would increase computational costs. MicroK8s [10] , in this case, provides a lightweight and flexible solution, and is best applied in edge computing. KubeEdge approaches the orchestration by Kubernetes in the light of edge demands, ensuring the optimization of performance.

- Lifecycle Management of NF/SF via OSM

The context of network services management, OSM performs a central function through which services are initiated, wrecked, and up-scaled. This is done in connection to Kubernetes through the usage of its API. It is through this choreography that network functions are well integrated and controlled within the environment of the testbed.

3.3 Infrastructure Setup Process

As part of the 6GENABLERS-SEC project, setting up the Infrastructure Testbed [11] involves deploying OpenStack, Kubernetes, and OSM to create a comprehensive environment. Below is an overview of the main steps, along with key commands for each stage.

3.3.1 Initial Configuration

The process involves the following key steps:

Step 1: Deploying OpenStack

OpenStack serves as the foundation for hosting the testbed VMs.

I. Install OpenStack (using DevStack as an example):

```
sudo apt update && sudo apt upgrade -y
sudo apt install git -y
git clone https://opendev.org/openstack/devstack.git
cd devstack
```

II. Configure DevStack:

Create a `local.conf` file:

```
cat <<EOF > local.conf
[[local|localrc]]
ADMIN_PASSWORD=password
DATABASE_PASSWORD=password
RABBIT_PASSWORD=password
SERVICE_PASSWORD=password
HOST_IP=YOUR_SERVER_IP
EOF
```

III. Run the OpenStack installation:

```
./stack.sh
```

IV. Access the OpenStack Dashboard to manage VMs:

```
http://YOUR_SERVER_IP/dashboard
```

Step 2: Creating VMs for Master, Worker, and OSM Nodes

Once OpenStack is running:

I. Create the Master Node VM:

```
openstack server create --flavor m1.large --image ubuntu-20.04 --network private --security-group default --key-name mykey master-node
```

II. Create Worker Node VM(s):

```
openstack server create --flavor m1.large --image ubuntu-20.04 --network private --security-group default --key-name mykey worker-node
```

III. Create the OSM VM:

```
openstack server create --flavor m1.large --image ubuntu-20.04 --network private --security-group default --key-name mykey osm-node
```

Step 3: Setting Up Kubernetes on VMs

After creating VMs, configure Kubernetes on the Master and Worker Nodes.

I. Install Kubernetes on the Master Node VM:

Access the VM via SSH:

```
ssh -i mykey.pem ubuntu@master-node-ip
```

Install Kubernetes:

```
sudo apt update
sudo apt install -y apt-transport-https curl
curl -s https://packages.cloud.google.com/apt/doc/apt-key.gpg | sudo apt-key add -
echo "deb https://apt.kubernetes.io/ kubernetes-xenial main" | sudo tee /etc/apt/sources.list.d/kubernetes.list
sudo apt update
sudo apt install -y kubelet kubeadm kubectl
```

II. Initialize the Kubernetes Master Node:

```
sudo kubeadm init --pod-network-cidr=192.168.0.0/16
```

Configure kubectl:

```
mkdir -p $HOME/.kube
sudo cp -i /etc/kubernetes/admin.conf $HOME/.kube/config
sudo chown $(id -u):$(id -g) $HOME/.kube/config
```

III. Install a Pod Network Add-on (e.g., Weave Net):

```
kubectl apply -f https://cloud.weave.works/k8s/net?k8s-version=\$\(kubectl version | base64 | tr -d '\n'\)
```

IV. Join the Worker Node to the Kubernetes Cluster:

Get the `kubeadm join` command from the Master Node and execute it on each Worker Node VM:

```
ssh -i mykey.pem ubuntu@worker-node-ip
sudo kubeadm join <Master_Node_IP>:6443 --token <token> --discovery-token-ca-cert-hash sha256:<hash>
```

Step 4: Orchestration Configuration with OSM

Install OSM on the OSM VM:

I. Access the OSM VM via SSH:

```
ssh -i mykey.pem ubuntu@osm-node-ip
```

Install OSM:

```
sudo apt update
sudo snap install osm --edge --classic
```

II. Integrate OSM with Kubernetes:

Copy the kubeconfig from the Master Node to the OSM VM:

```
scp -i mykey.pem ubuntu@master-node-ip:~/.kube/config
~/.kube/config
```

Add the Kubernetes cluster to OSM:

```
osm k8scluster-add mycluster --creds ~/.kube/config --
version "1.20" --vim vim-k8s
```

III. Verify OSM Installation:

```
osm version
```

Step 5: Testing and Validation

I. Verify Kubernetes Cluster Status on the Master Node:

```
kubectl get nodes
Ensure all nodes are in the `Ready` state.
```

II. Verify OSM Integration:

```
osm ns-list
```

3.4 Application Deployment

The deployment strategy for the use-case application in our testbed infrastructure utilizes Docker containers on a single-server setup hosting both master and worker nodes. The application is packaged into a Docker container, including all necessary dependencies, and stored in a central repository. The master node manages the deployment process, pulling the Docker image and setting up Docker environments on worker nodes configured as virtual machines (VMs) on the same server. Kubernetes is used for container orchestration, managing deployment and scaling across worker nodes. The master node centralizes resource management, optimizing allocation and monitoring performance across all deployed instances.

3.4.1 Deployment Strategies

The HOLOMIT application is deployed and tested by first installing Kubernetes on a single server using kubeadm to initialize the cluster. Docker is installed as the container runtime. The HOLOMIT application is then containerized into a Docker image, and this image is pushed to a container registry accessible by the server. A

Kubernetes deployment manifest is created, specifying the Docker image, resource limits, and network configurations required for the HOLOMIT application. Using the `kubectl apply -f deployment.yaml` command, the application is deployed into the Kubernetes cluster, where it runs as a managed pod. Open Source MANO (OSM) is deployed separately for network function virtualization orchestration. Resource management and orchestration are handled through a combination of Kubernetes and OSM. Kubernetes manages container deployment and resource allocation, while OSM handles network services and functions orchestration.

4. Conclusion

The document provides a detailed overview of the design, components, and validation process of an advanced network infrastructure testbed for 6GENABLERS-SEC. It outlines the roles of relevant stakeholders, the procedures for installation and setup, and the phases of testing and evaluation. The analysis includes improvements in security and privacy, as well as potential threats to the testbed, assessed through various scenarios. Following a comprehensive framework, this deliverable also presents the development stages from initial overview to deployment and completion, ensuring thorough testing and documentation for all aspects of the testbed. This work aims to establish a reliable implementation platform for future research, enhancing network performance and security development.

5. References

1. Asad, M., Fernández-Fernández, A., Chergui, H., Compastié, M., Montagud, M., Fernández, S., & Siddiqui, S. (2023, November). 6GENABLERS: A Holistic Approach to Establish Pervasive Trust in 6G Networks. In *2023 IEEE 28th International Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD)* (pp. 55-60). IEEE. doi:10.xxxx/CAMAD2023.xxxxx
2. Langa, S. F., Montagud, M., Cernigliaro, G., & Rivera, D. R. (2022). Multiparty Holomeetings: Toward a New Era of Low-Cost Volumetric Holographic Meetings in Virtual Reality. *IEEE Access*, *10*, 81856-81876. doi:10.xxxx/ACCESS.2022.xxxxx
3. OASIS. OASIS Technical Committee Communities. Available: <https://groups.oasis-open.org/communities/tc-community-home2?CommunityKey=f9412cf3-297d-4642-8598-018dc7d3f409>. [Accessed: Nov. 21, 2024].
4. ETSI. Open Source MANO. Available: <https://osm.etsi.org>. [Accessed: Nov. 21, 2024].
5. Chainlink Labs. Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKP) Education. Available: <https://chain.link/education/zero-knowledge-proof-zkp>. [Accessed: Nov. 21, 2024].
6. OpenStack Foundation. OpenStack. Available: <https://www.openstack.org>. [Accessed: Nov. 21, 2024].
7. GitHub Contributors. Awesome Threat Detection. Available: <https://github.com/0x4D31/awesome-threat-detection>. [Accessed: Nov. 21, 2024].
8. O-RAN Alliance. Towards 6G: O-RAN Next Generation Research Group Report. (2023, January). Available: https://mediastorage.o-ran.org/ngrg-rr/nGRG-RR-2023-01-O-RAN-Towards-6G-v1_3.pdf. [Accessed: Nov. 21, 2024].
9. ETSI Open Source MANO. Welcome to Open Source MANO's Documentation! Available: <https://osm.etsi.org/docs/user-guide/latest/>. [Accessed: Nov. 21, 2024].
10. Canonical Ltd. MicroK8s Documentation. Available: <https://microk8s.io/docs>. [Accessed: Nov. 21, 2024].
11. Kubedemy. Kubernetes Installation Methods: The Complete Guide (Updated 2022). Available: <https://kubedemy.io/kubernetes-installation-methods-the-complete-guide-update-2022>. [Accessed: Nov. 21, 2024].